

Talk like Jane Austen - A deep neural network for artificial text generation

Alexander Teusz

University of Dusseldorf

Department of Language and Information

alexander.teusz@hhu.de

Abstract

In this paper we develop a neural network model with Python and Keras to figure out if it is possible to teach a machine to generate texts such as humans. We perform two different experiments with the same LSTM model and compare them in relation to linguistic aspects.

1 Introduction

The third wave of Artificial Intelligence is becoming more powerful from year to year and even creative tasks are solved by computers, since the auction house Christie's sold a painting drawn by an algorithm (Cohn, 2018). Thus it should be possible to write literary stories like one of the most famous authors – Jane Austen. In relation to machine learning techniques, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) are very powerful models that pay attention on temporal sequences like a chain of words. In this paper I demonstrate the power of RNNs by implementing a neural network model that is able to produce text like Jane Austen, furthermore I discuss why it's difficult to train sequence based models and what could be improved related to linguistic aspects.

Therefore the research questions of this paper are if it is possible to produce human-like text without teaching the computer about syntax, morphology or other linguistic theories and what are the best conditions in terms of chosen features and the length of information sequences – how many different pieces of information can the model process at one go.

The state of the art work shows that there are different ways to solve this task such as Xie says in his practical guide. Most solutions are using the character based model where the model creates words by concatenating characters, such as

Hadifar or Brownlee. For this reason, this paper uses a word based LSTM (section 2.2.1) model where one hypothesis is that the model will produce meaningful text for a small set of monitored words and the other hypothesis says that we don't need to train the model for more than 20 epochs to predict understandable text.

Related to the state of the art work, a word based model is a good choice for context prediction since it doesn't have to produce words, so that the words are always written correctly. Because of that the model is able to predict a related word for this previous one. A problem could be the grammatical changes of a word such as plural or the difference between *he* and *him*. Finally, if the model has to process too many words, it won't be able to write a full related sentence as there are too many different possibilities to learn. Therefore the basic difference between this paper and the compared ones is the basis of the monitored tokens – character based and word based.

To solve the mentioned task, some steps have to be taken. First, the data set has to include as many words as possible to represent a whole language, since this set of words will be the base of all AI written texts, but too many words could be unfavorable as well as the neural network would have too many possibilities for the next word to predict, such as mentioned before. Second, there has to be such a neural network that is able to learn the context between a written sentence and its meaning to create meaningful content; for example the word order such as *I am falling* and not *I falling am*. This task can be taken over by recurrent neural networks that have the ability to note chronological orders.

2 Recurrent Neural Networks

A Recurrent Neural Network allows us to model sequential data (Sutskever et al., 2011). That means, it is possible to remember previous information such as a word or a frame since the network processes a sequence of various data of a specific length – in our case, words.

We humans are doing the same every time we read, think or speak. We "don't throw everything away and start thinking from scratch again" (Olah, 2015). There is always an information stored in our memory which could help us understanding the current.

With the functionality of remembering information there are several tasks we can do:

- Speech and text generation
- Translation of text in another language
- Predict share prices

Conventional feed-forward networks are only able to handle the entire data sequence at once in a huge vector and turn it to a single data point (Chollet, 2017, 196).

2.1 How it works

To note the information that was created before, the neural network has to store all predictions in a temporal storage. Like the name "recurrent" says the network repeats a period of steps on itself. Like Chollet shows in figure 1, the RNN

Figure 1: A recurrent network: a network with a loop (Chollet, 2017, 196)

has a recurrent connection where the output will be the input of the next element in our sequence. It stores a current state t and iterates over the sequence of data like for example a sentence with 10 words which are stored in a 2D vector with the shape $(timesteps, input_features)$ where the time step is the number of monitored words in our data

set and the features are the numerical representation of these words. Within the loop a function f uses the the current input and state to create the next output.

2.2 Different types of RNNs

For completing the tasks shown in section 2 there are different types of RNNs who are responsible for one specific job. Without naming all, this paper uses the "Many-To-Many" network for text generation (Karpathy, 2015). The network gets an input

Figure 2: Many-To-Many RNN

sequence, processes the elements and outputs a sequence of predicted elements. In translation, the length of both sequences would be the same, if the text in the original language has the same length than the text in the translated language. In text generation, however, it processes a sequence of a defined length and outputs each word in relation to its predecessor. How many words the generator shell predict depends on the configuration.

2.2.1 Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

Even if they are the basis layer for chronological sequences, there is one decisive problem with standard Recurrent Neural Networks – long-term dependencies such as long sentences are impossible to learn (Chollet, 2017, 202). It is possible to predict the last word of a sentence with simple RNNs as we don't need more than the previous words and no context: "The clouds are in the sky". It is clear that the clouds are located in the sky but if we want to predict the word *French* in "I grew up in France I speak fluent *French*." the neural network has to understand the context between the country France and its national language (Olah, 2015). This problem is solved by LSTM which were introduced by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber in 1997. Instead of a single \tanh layer the LSTM uses four layers to remember information

and decide if the current data is good enough to store. The feature which makes the LSTM irreplaceable is the cell state, a conveyor of information who "runs straight down the entire chain" (Olah, 2015). To prevent that only necessary information are promoted, gates are used to remove or add data to the current state. Unlike the Simple RNN the LSTM uses three *sigmoid* layers next to the *tanh*. The *sigmoid* returns a number between 0 and 1 where 0 means that the current data should get stored and 1 means the exact opposite (Olah, 2015). With this technique the network could be able to understand that the country *France* and the language *French* are related to each other.

2.3 Backpropagation

However, understanding data can't be successful if the network only learns straight forward without adapting the already learned. Nowadays the algorithm of choice is the so called *Backpropagation* which, in short, uses the loss value to adjust the weights of our layers. That means the chosen loss value will get decreased by going forward and backward. Each step contributes that the weights are becoming more harmonized so that the loss function is reduced and the prediction is more realistic, as explained by Williams, Hinton and Rumelhart (Rumelhart et al., 1985) and Chollet, 52.

2.4 Word Vectors (Word Embeddings)

With the *Backpropagation* algorithm the neural network has the capability to adjust all calculated weights, but there is no understanding about the word context, yet. For this task it would be helpful to not look at words as unique symbols rather as related meaningful sequences of characters, which have similarities and dissimilarities. The common paradigm for deriving such representations is based on the distributional hypothesis of Harris. He says that words in similar contexts have similar meanings. Therefore the literature has changed; now a word is represented by a "word-context matrix M in which each row i corresponds to a word, each column j to a context in which the word appeared, and each matrix entry M_{ij} corresponds to some association measure between the word and the context." (Levy and Goldberg, 2014, 1). These presentations seems to work well in various NLP tasks by virtue of the paper by Turian et al. that came to the conclusion that "word embeddings [...] can improve the accuracy of a near-state-

of-the-art supervised NLP system" (Turian et al., 2010, 392). With this functionality the system is able to learn that the words *Queen* and *King* are similar to each other, same as *Paris*, *France* and *Capital*. There are a few pretrained word embeddings which are free to use out there, though this paper trains own word vectors corresponding the used data set.

3 Dataset and Methods

For predicting text sequences, this paper uses Googles Python library Keras in version 2.2.4 which is based on Tensorflow (Google, 2019) – the Python version has to be 3.6. For monitoring the current results, Keras offers the *ModelCheckpoint* which stores the weights of the previous epoch in an *hdf5* file. Thus, the developer can abort the training. Here, the model is based on the *Sequential* Keras class. Furthermore, a Python script vectorizes the data set, builds the model and fits the neural network related to the data set. Since neural networks are using GPUs for fitting the model, an Amazon Web Services (AWS) EC2 instance and a specialized computer in the institute of computational linguistics are used in this paper for training the weights. Without a GPU, the process of fitting would take too much time for this study.

3.1 Preprocessing

The data set includes all books by Jane Austen in English¹, concatenated and without the credits. It contains a total of 950,740 words using 22,336 different tokens as shown below – punctuation included.

- (1) The family of Dashwood had long been settled in Sussex. Their estate was large, and their residence was at Norland Park, in the centre of their property, where, for many generations, they had lived in so respectable a manner as to engage [...]

For text generation there is no need to create a CSV file that contains features in columns because our network doesn't aim to predict a value c based on columns a and b but wants to learn the spelling and words of a specific language. Because of that all punctuation and line breaks are important information.

¹<https://www.fulltextarchive.com/search/jane+austen/>

Figure 3: Anatomy of an LSTM (Chollet, 2017, 204)

3.1.1 Extract words from the data set

Accordingly, this paper uses the *CountVectorizer* by *Scikit Learn* to build a vocabulary over the whole set of tokens. This is not necessarily the main application of this class but thus it is possible to train the neural network with a specific number of words, the 1000 most common for example. The *CountVectorizer* at the end returns a list of all distinct words, by which the length of this list is related to our *maximum of features* we want to use.

3.1.2 Converting words into numbers

After extracting all tokens into a list, this list has to be transformed into numbers as there is no ability to train the model with words. Therefore you use two dictionaries, *word_to_int* and *int_to_word* which will include the word as a key on the left side and the value, the index number on the right side – opposite for the *int_to_word* dictionary.

Now, every word is represented by its index in the list of *tokens_transformed* with which it is clearly recognizable. This isn't only important for the process of training but also for predicting words afterwards. For predicting a new word the script has to know which word is represented by a specific index. If the script predicts the number 214, the result has to be *hello*, and so on.

3.1.3 Defining training data

With this list called *tokens_transformed* it is now possible to define the *X* and *y* matrices, which are necessary for a Keras neural network. Normal Python arrays would not provide the required functionalities, since neural networks are working with matrix multiplications. The solution are *numpy arrays* by *SciPy* – the two arrays are not simply merged, rather each element is multiplied by the other.

The whole data set is now well prepared and ready for being the basis of our training process.

3.2 The model

For this study the paper used one Embedding layer, two LSTM layers and a Dense layer for the output such as shown in the figure 4. The Em-

Figure 4: The chosen model

bedding layer is used for teaching the network contexts between various words such as *man* and *woman*. This shall improve the choice of the next word in our prediction (section 2.4). The two LSTM layers are learning the context between whole sentences as explained in section 2.2.1. The Dense layer's output is presented as a vector filled with the probabilities of all used words to predict the most common word at position $i+1$.

The chosen input shapes are (100, 40) and (1000, 40). First, the one hundred most common words in the data set are used for this model in which a sequence of 40 words is monitored at the same time to learn the context between a dot and a written word starting with an upper-case letter, for example. The second process of fitting uses 1000 words to enhance the variation.

For compiling the model, a *RMSprop* optimizer is used whose task it is to reduce the loss value. As the output is a vector with the length 100 or 1000,

the chosen loss function is a *categorical cross entropy*. Table 1 provides an overview of the hyper-parameters I used for the text generation model.

Layer	Hyper-parameters	Value
Embedding	input shape	40
	output dim.	100
LSTM	units	256
LSTM	units	256
Dense	units	32
	activation	softmax

Table 1: Hyper-parameters of the model

3.3 Predicting text

In text prediction / generation there are a few steps to follow. First, there has to be a basis from that the generation will start, whereby the data set must be read in. Second, the model learned to predict numbers, not words and these numbers represent indexes of words in the text. To connect the predicted index with the correct word, the dictionary files have to be read in either. Now the basis is given but there is no prediction process yet, why the trained model has to be included.

The model contains all weights for all words the neural network monitored. Now it should be possible to predict the most probable word after *she*, for example. You have to define the starting point of the prediction based on the data set. If the sentence is "By a former marriage, Mr. Henry Dashwood had one son: by his present lady," the text to predict would be "three daughters." if the neural network learned everything – why this prediction wouldn't be the actual task of a text generation, the section 5 discusses. A loop predicts a specific number of words. For each word, the Keras function *predict()* is used to get a vector of 100 or 1000 probabilities. These 100 or 1000 probabilities represent the words the neural network learned in the first process of fitting. Since it could be the case that the generated text would be a sequence of same words, a numpy random function is used to choose random probabilities from the *prediction* vector. Otherwise the output would be such as "her and her her and her her and her her" because the prediction always chooses the most probable word for the word *i-1* and this is the same as in the previous step. As mentioned before the *print()* function uses the *int_to_word* dictionary to get the word of the predicted index. The last step is to append the

predicted word to the sentence, thus the basis for the next prediction is given.

4 Experiments and Results

This study fitted the model two times with different configurations.

4.1 Experiment 1: 100 Words, 10 Epochs

The first one only monitored the one hundred most common words, in which the result isn't as realistic as it has to be. After 20 epochs the accuracy was 0.2426 – that means the model learned a quarter of the entire text context:

100 Words, 20 Epochs			
Epoch	Loss Value	Accuracy	Validation Accuracy
01/20	2.7351	0.2252	0.2014
02/20	2.6824	0.2340	0.2136
03/20	2.6744	0.2361	0.2165
04/20	2.6629	0.2379	0.2155
05/20	2.6749	0.2393	0.2126
06/20	2.6972	0.2390	0.2178
07/20	2.6589	0.2400	0.2153
08/20	2.6592	0.2409	0.2183
09/20	2.6572	0.2406	0.2195
10/20	2.6581	0.2414	0.2163
11/20	2.6581	0.2420	0.2160
12/20	2.6568	0.2419	0.2208
13/20	2.6593	0.2420	0.2073
14/20	2.6584	0.2424	0.2215
15/20	2.6596	0.2423	0.2103
16/20	2.6581	0.2422	0.2176
17/20	2.6587	0.2425	0.2180
18/20	2.6587	0.2427	0.2170
19/20	2.6552	0.2428	0.2154
20/20	2.6569	0.2426	0.2128

Table 2: Results for 100 Words and 20 Epochs

Each epoch needed 10 minutes on the average and trained 256,346 out of a total of 320,435 tokens – the rest is used for validation. Keras offers a simple way to split the whole data set into two different sets – the train and test set. The method *fit()* has a parameter named *validation_split* which accepts a decimal number between 0 and 1. This study uses a validation split of 0.2 (20%). The used shape looks such as the following:

```
X Shape : (320435, 40)
y Shape : (320435,)
```

The y vector has no second parameter as it isn't One-Hot encoded because this step is covered by the Embedding layer.

If we take a look at figure 5 we see that the *accuracy* increased sharply for the first 2 epochs but then has settled. Unlike the *validation accuracy* which is tested with the 20% testing data. It has a lot of peaks after epoch ten and at the end it decreases.

Figure 5: Accuracy for 100 Words and 20 Epochs

4.2 Experiment 2: 1000 Words, 20 Epochs

In the second fit we're using the 1000 most common words but the accuracy deteriorates since there are too many connections to learn in the context of this study such as shown in the following shape:

```
X Shape : (539719, 40)
y Shape : (539719,)
```

The model would examine 219,284 more words, even if there are only 22,336 distinct tokens in the data set (section 3.1). The second try only fitted the model in 10 epochs and each epoch took almost 17 minutes, in which the accuracy didn't get better than 19.59% as shown in table 4.2 and visualized in figure 6.

The last epoch only reached an accuracy of 18.23% so that we can predict that the accuracy

1000 Words, 10 Epochs			
Epoch	Loss Value	Accuracy	Validation Accuracy
01/20	3.8347	0.1681	0.1644
02/20	3.7021	0.1865	0.1748
03/20	3.7089	0.1906	0.1690
04/20	3.6747	0.1935	0.1732
05/20	3.6875	0.1940	0.1778
06/20	3.6950	0.1953	0.1710
07/20	3.7874	0.1947	0.1805
08/20	3.6974	0.1961	0.1712
09/20	3.7073	0.1959	0.1777
10/20	4.5662	0.1823	0.1756

Table 3: Results for 1000 Words and 10 Epochs

would not have improved significantly. In figure 6 you can see that the *accuracy* increased very sharply but dropped of a lot after epoch 8. Such as in figure 5 the *validation accuracy* has a lot of peaks and doesn't decrease as it should do in the best case. After 10 epochs the model didn't learn enough information to predict permanent correct words, or even words that are related to the last one in a basic way. Thus the text generation for these two experiments could be very interesting.

Figure 6: Accuracy for 1000 Words and 10 Epochs

4.3 Text generation

In text generation the accuracy is not this important as the generated could be still meaningful. Furthermore, it is very interesting to know if the number of observed words affects the quality of the text and how many predicted words are connected in terms of contexts.

The first text generation uses the model with the

100 most common words, which trained for 20 epochs. The most meaningful results are marked as bold; to concentrate on contexts, the punctuation are excluded – except dashes:

- (2) The of was of in a of her was to in the had and very was to was the in her sister in the to the and the and his and was of his had been so and her to and was a **had her family** of at of his was to to his in was so as was as to his his in very the Dashwood his very and was as to for a as was was as to her and in was a for the which to and his as her was to and to her for of the long and as as of of her to in **was a good to** the of the was to the of which was for and to had for the of been the in of the they of to the of **as the life of a** in which to and **had been in the family of** to of and of which and

Even if the total result isn't meaningful and connected, several parts are significant. The second fit (3) used the 1000 most common words and only 10 epochs since the training time was too long:

- (3) young a his good been from will any for own all that be much to well of the very father such an man in every – to very hope in it of **only to be the time he** that he not so very nature as where him The of him all nothing for the for there were of will not be their be what to be **was to make** to his all they **not have been** to it two **to be that** had from from in the of the and not so as it for only not pleasure **of more than by him and that it was her** with her in his it could not what was **as a present from her** the of her mother and a very woman in to the of which her to her that had He himself and his was all Mrs as be for her long her known for was in what are a of him two are to **from him** most and are

Due to the 900 more words, the variation of the language is much more pronounced than in text generation (2). The network learned for example that *more than* is a typical English phrase or *that it was her* – It predicted four words in a connected sequence, same as *as a present from her*, which could be a functional relative sentence in English. Very interesting is the prediction of the dash in line 3. For some learned reason, a dash appears to come after the word *every* in the data set. How-

ever, because of Word Embedding, it could also be a word that is semantically linked to *every*.

4.4 Evaluation

As Xie presents, there is no automated metric for generated texts such as a confusion matrix (Xie, 2017, 12). Even if the ROGUE/BE by Lin has become the standard toolkit for evaluating machine-generated texts, in their case summaries, the correlation of this score with human evaluation has not been consistent (Conroy and Dang, 2008, 145). Since it is based on n-grams, it is only a rough approximation, why "manual human evaluation should be interspersed as well" (Xie, 2017, 12). Therefore, I evaluated the generated text as a human being. If a human reads a text he/she takes a look at the understandable phrases or sentences to develop the content of the document. In this study, the results are not perfect but you can see that the network learned basic phrases and word orders such as shown in section 4. The aim of this paper is to show that it is possible to teach a computer how to talk like a human, in this case Jane Austen. Without teaching the model about syntax, morphology or other linguistic theories the computer reached a total of 11 meaningful phrases in 400 predicted words, divided into two steps. Except one phrase in (3) that could be a relative sentence, there are no specific and meaningful sentences in both predictions. Since the model is word based we don't have to take a specific look at the word generations but you can see that the model learned the meaning of the word *him* which is used as a dative in the phrase *of him* in prediction (3). Even if those patterns are trivial for humans, the model had to learn the meaning of *her* and *him*; another example shows that this was successful: *with her and his* in prediction (3). Finally the model wasn't able to learn more linguistic rules as we trained it only with 100 and 1000 unique words of a total of more than 22,000. In relation to a technical interpretation, the model has to learn much more different words from the data set to write grammatically correct sentences. Since the model just read the data set, the linguistic interpretation could be that those words who were learned, are correct.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

In section 3.3 it says that the aim of a LSTM text generation model is not to get an accuracy of 100%. If it would be the case, the model maybe

would only predict the exact text from the data set or it would have learned the entire context of the trained scope and writes meaningful sentences that are related to each other. This would be an interesting research question for a future work. Over and above, that the current model isn't using a specific word embedding such as GloVe² or ELMo³, while ELMo would be a interesting case in a future work since ELMo is the latest word embedding out there as it was published in 2018. With those word embeddings, the Keras Embedding Layer could use their weights instead of generating new weights with the given data set, what maybe would decrease the time of fitting. Even if those embeddings aren't necessary trained with Jane Austens' books, they are used successfully in other projects and could increase the number of meaningful predicted phrases in our generated text, significant.

Due to the fact that the model was trained relatively little, one process could fit the same model once for 40, 60 or 80 epochs. Hadifar says in the Keras Text Generation Example that there were 20 epochs required to get an coherent result (Hadifar, 2018). To get a more complex model a future work could include more hidden layers, such as a second Dense or more LSTM layers. Even if the complicity rises, the result also could be sobering because more complicity doesn't promise a better result. However, with the use of a Dropout Layer, the model could learn by itself that it's not the normal pattern to repeat words infinitely often such as I showed in section 3.3. Therefore the text generator wouldn't need a *random* function to get around that problem.

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²<https://nlp.stanford.edu/projects/glove/>

³<https://allennlp.org/elmo>

Appendix

Create model

```
from nltk.tokenize import word_tokenize
import nltk
import numpy as np
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Dense, LSTM,
    Embedding
from keras.callbacks import
    ModelCheckpoint
from keras.utils import to_categorical
import pickle
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text
    import CountVectorizer

nltk.download("punkt")

"""
Constants
"""
SEQUENCELENGTH = 10
MAXFEATURES = 1000

"""
load the data from our dataset
"""
with open("../data/jane_austen.txt", "r"
    , encoding="utf-8") as file:
    contents = file.read()
data = "\n".join(contents.split("\n"))

"""
split the whole text into word tokens
related to a CountVectorizer
"""
tokens = word_tokenize(data)

print("Tokens: ", len(tokens))
print("Set of Tokens: ", len(set(tokens)
    ))

cv = CountVectorizer(lowercase=False ,
    token_pattern="(.*)" , max_features=
    MAXFEATURES)

# Hiermit wird ein Vokabular aufgebaut ,
welches sich ber den gesamten
input Text streckt
cv.fit(tokens)

# Dies muss nun extrahiert werden //
Array mapping from feature integer
indices to feature name
# gibt eine liste mit allen w rtern
z r ck .
features = cv.get_feature_names()

"""
specify a number for each word since the
neural network can only handle
numbers
"""
word_to_int = {}
int_to_word = {}

# get the index for each word in a
dictionary
for i in range(0, len(features)):
```

```
word = tokens[i]
word_to_int[word] = i
int_to_word[i] = word

#convert each word to the index in the
word_to_int dictionary
tokens_transformed = [word_to_int[word]
    for word in tokens if word in
    word_to_int]

"""
Preparation for training
"""
# MARK: - One Hot Encoding it not
required since the Embedding Layer
will do this
X = []
y = []

for i in range(0, len(tokens_transformed)
    ) - SEQUENCELENGTH):
    X.append(tokens_transformed[i:i +
        SEQUENCELENGTH])
    y.append(tokens_transformed[i +
        SEQUENCELENGTH])

X = np.array(X)
y = np.array(y)

print("X Shape: ", X.shape)
print("y Shape: ", y.shape)

"""
Build the model
"""
model = Sequential()
model.add(Embedding(cv.max_features ,
    100, input_shape=(SEQUENCELENGTH,)))
model.add(LSTM(256, return_sequences=
    True))
model.add(LSTM(256, return_sequences=
    False))
#model.add(Dense(1000, activation="
sigmoid"))
model.add(Dense(cv.max_features ,
    activation="softmax"))

model.compile(optimizer="adam", loss="
categorical_crossentropy", metrics=[
"accuracy"])

"""
Train the neural network
"""
checkpoint = ModelCheckpoint("../results
/40 Epochs/weights/jane_austen.{epoch
:02d}-{val_loss:.2f}.hdf5")
model.fit(
    X,
    to_categorical(y, num_classes=cv.
max_features),
    epochs=10,
    batch_size=32,
    validation_split=0.2,
    callbacks=[checkpoint]
)

"""
Get a summery and save the data
```

```

"""
model.summary()
model.save("../results/40Epochs/
jane_austen.model")

with open("../results/40Epochs/pickles/
word_to_int.pickle", "wb") as file:
    pickle.dump(word_to_int, file)

with open("../results/40Epochs/pickles/
int_to_word.pickle", "wb") as file:
    pickle.dump(int_to_word, file)

```

Predict text

```

import nltk
import pickle
from keras.models import load_model
import numpy as np

with open("../data/jane_austen.txt", "r"
, encoding="utf-8") as file:
    contents = file.read()

contents = contents.split("\n")
contents = [line.strip() for line in
contents]
contents = "\n".join(contents)

tokens = nltk.word_tokenize(contents)

with open("../results/1000Words_10Epochs
/pickles/word_to_int.pickle", "rb")
as file:
    word_to_int = pickle.load(file)

with open("../results/1000Words_10Epochs
/pickles/int_to_word.pickle", "rb")
as file:
    int_to_word = pickle.load(file)

tokens_transformed = [word_to_int[word]
for word in tokens if word in
word_to_int]

"""
load model
"""
model = load_model("../results/1000
Words_10Epochs/jane_austen.model")

"""
predict text with random parts
"""
sentence = np.array(tokens_transformed
[2000:2040])

for i in range(0, 200):
    prediction = model.predict(sentence.
reshape(1, 40))
    word = np.random.choice(len(
int_to_word), p=prediction[0])
    print(int_to_word[word].replace(",","
").replace(".",","), end=" ")
    sentence = np.append(sentence[1:], [
word])

```